

How to Create a MIMS

Creating a MIMS - consciously - given what we currently know

Part of the Continuing Series on the Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual realms.
A metaphysical and philosophical treatise, inspired by the EPEMC framework

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ABSTRACT

The author has had a number of positive experiences in utilizing this philosophy, which is an original fruit of the Extended Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology. Though he has not been able to test the Dual Layer Economics¹, he feels that several other examples of use have created positive conditions to warrant an explanation of the utility of this philosophy beyond mere empirical observation of *results*. Note that the hypotheses in MIMS 2.0+ have not yet been verified or validated². Nevertheless, they will be used. This is a philosophy paper, after all. In the end analysis only individual rigor and a compilation of case studies, as well as accumulation of data from the business, finance, analytics/data, statistics, and all things fortunate in general will result in true validation. Such a cross study could take a decade or more. In order to facilitate this experiment, the author is mimsically introducing the pathway in this paper, to save time. If more people know how, then the experiment accelerates. Therefore the paper is itself a MIMS (in the futurization category). Categories will begin to be identified, though there may likely be more than can be known at this time, or even an infinite variety. Pragmatically speaking, there are only 8 worthy categories.

KEYWORDS - MIMS, Philosophy, EPEMC, Cosmology, Materialism, Spirituality

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https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

² https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

Introduction

The author is currently making a MIMS. Not this paper, although that is true³, but the EPEMC Gateway. The purpose of the Gateway⁴ is for education, the establishment of a syncretic community within the PEM framework, and to showcase the hard work of the author and other researchers. It is also designed to be up to modern standards. The previous iterations, the Electric Universe Gateway, and The Pulse, are now defunct. There's a need - a niche to fill, so to speak - in the educational department, and web 2.0 enables the author to quickly build it.

How is this a MIMS? The author's desire to increase educational outreach and awareness of the plasma-electromagnetic cosmology, as well as eliminate sectarian division in the altstream of cosmology, acts as the "spiritual" aspect within the person. Then the author's use of the PEMF, as well as personal bioelectrical energy (calories) and flux (time), enables ideas to emerge from the counterspace (unknown) and Aether, to come through the author into material form (a website). Its use has already begun being proved as a live-streamed show regarding some of the author's papers was aired in the previous night.⁵ Therefore, the MIMS is not even yet complete and already it is bringing material benefit for it drove viewers towards the embedded papers, and produced good messaging. How did this relate, in a concrete way, to the spiritual? The author has received from a viewer of a previous MIMS show⁶, the following words,

"Hello Shifu,

Trusting you are well. Apologies for emailing you here. I couldn't find an email address in the EPEMC website.

I couldn't find the MIMS on Ether, Fortune and Business and also, I am looking for one where you talk about who's the Big G (God).

I am very interested in reading this as I continue following a nudge to learn about the God, Jesus, where is the soul created, fortune and the universe.

When you have a spare moment, can you please let me know where I can find MIMS on these subjects. Perhaps the title is different and that's why I can find them in the search.

This is just for my own personal growth and development. ...

Thank you for answering back.

Blessings,

[name withheld]"⁷

When provided with the Gateway link, this person was able to view the information - and the Directory⁸ - quickly. This form of circular redundancy is typical of the spirality of the "Big G".⁹ The taking of the

³ He has a desire to see people try to engineer better futures and lives for themselves, as well as to spread the philosophy.

⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway>

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IHdyXMNrur4>

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VMROMCfX3ZQ>

⁷ Date: Wed, Sep 29, 2021 at 10:02 AM

Subject: Question regarding Shifu's Leak Project Episode (MIMS)

⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc>

⁹ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

information from the PPPC¹⁰ and making it no longer idea, but concrete results, enabled engagement on a higher level.

This then was considered a positive experience, for both people. This closes the loop.

How these kinds of tools and projects, and other products and services in a human (and world) needs centered marketplace works is of vital importance to the study of how to “save” mankind from its own amnesia-induced path of self-destruction¹¹, bacchian¹² annihilation¹³, and of course, does pertain to the wellbeing of the human soul or psyche itself. While we must “digitize”¹⁴ spirit in science and even science based philosophies, we cannot eliminate the consciousness aspect, and therefore its relation to the *L* power of the self-consistent “Big G.”

We should, instead, embrace it. This is not circular logic but an ecosystem. And like the “water cycle” things take many forms before being reintroduced. Consider the 6 segments of the “Big G” diagram, and its implied 4 part PPPC. These are reflected (and perhaps inspired) by the Chinese sciences and Natural Philosophy¹⁵. There is certainly an internal and external self consistent rigor¹⁶ that appears as a continuous spectrum between PEMC, Chinese Science, Egyptian Science, and comparative mythology. But we digress.

Table 1 - Comparing MIMS and Chinese Natural Philosophy’s “*P* power” applications

MIMS		Chinese Science (Medicine in this case)	
1. Potentiality	- X?	1. Yin or Yang	
2. Possibility	- Y/N	2. Hot or Cold	
3. Probability	- %	3. Excess or Deficient	
4. Cloud (or matrix)	- form	4. Inside or Outside	
1. L power		1. Taiyang	Greatest Yang
2. F power		2. Yangming	Yang Brightness
3. A power		3. Shaoyang	Lesser Yang
4. N power		4. Taiyin	Greater Yin
5. P power		5. Shaoyin	Lesser Yin
6. G power		6. Jueyin	Reverting Yin

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/50912946/FAQ_EPEMC_MIMS

¹¹ “Mankind in Amnesia,” I. Velikovsky, 1982

¹²

https://www.academia.edu/37403915/Ferris_Wheels_and_the_Dionysian_Irony_The_subconscious_drive_of_thrill_abandonment_of_caution_and_the_motifs_of_Amusement_Park_rides

¹³

https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of_US_Military_Dominance_from_an_Art_of_War_perspective_and_MIMS_Analysis_as_well_as_a_short_discussion_of_the_history_of_failures_of_government_programs_from_antiquity_through_the_Great_Enlightenment

¹⁴ Called “sampling” in music; http://users.ece.utexas.edu/~valvano/Volume1/E-Book/C13_DACSound.htm

¹⁵ https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC

¹⁶ https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

Steps in Composing a MIMS

1. Identify a need.
2. Translate into a desire.
3. Align the need with the desire, or the desire with the need.
4. Visualize a solution set (hypotheses).
 - a. More ideas is better than few.
 - b. Can include futurism concepts.
 - c. Measurable goals exceed immeasurable ones.
5. Construct a framework (experiment).
 - a. Include the potentially infinite within a finite construct.
 - b. Concentrate upon organizational apparatus.
6. Devote resources.
7. Focus upon the flux (timing) and the potentiality of success.
 - a. See the probability increasing.
8. Measure results.
 - a. Accept unexplained consequences either with humility or attention/interest.
9. Repeat favorable outcomes.

Improving Results

The author might seem like an expert in this philosophy, being the originator. But actually he feels like a complete neophyte. It is an area that seems to have many other masters and experts (from the perspective of manifestation, or “law of attraction” etc.). However, the author is an expert in converting bad fortune into favorable circumstances. Therefore, there are a few key aspects to consider when designing or improving one’s MIMS:

- Consider the timing of the creation and *application*
 - All MIMS have timing appropriateness.¹⁷
- Consider also the effects of PEMF conditions - such as solar wind, moon phase, weather, etc. - upon your experiment. Just because your MIMS did not work at that moment does not guarantee it was a “bad idea”
- Consider the current status of Shi (positional advantage, etc.) in yourself, your MIMS, your ability to apply it with rigor, scientifically, dispassionately (unless it requires passion and emotion), over a consistent trek to weigh outcomes
- Consider the origin of the motivation - could it be partially an anti-MIMS? (like revenge, or greed)
- Consider the extenuating factors and circumstances which alter the PPC
- Attempt corrections to the model before abandonment
- Patch up weaknesses in a MIMS and retest
- Apply wisdom wherever possible
- Consider not only power in application, but access, influence, and affluence as side conditions that affect the outcomes
- Examine faulty instrumentation (usually yourself), tools, and data with brutal self-honesty¹⁸

¹⁷ While social media seems a lot like IRC and AOL Instant Messenger, SM apps are currently en vogue. But some have already died or declined. This means the functional need was not the cause. It was other conditions, and the Changes.

¹⁸ “The market is never wrong.”

Conclusion

By creating your own MIMS, testing them, and repeating the adventure, you might be capable of futurising your present. It does appear to be a scientific process, and this might be on account of the Scientific Method itself being a MIMS. MIMS are capable to: daisy-chain, compound, and piggyback upon one another, and they might be non-linear as well. Be open to many potential PPC variables, and control the controls strictly. Please report back to the author the results of any findings, preferably with detailed data analysis.

References

1. "On the Membranous Interface of the Material and the Spiritual (from an EPEMC perspective) & Dual/Double Layer Economics... a proposed test of EPEMC's 'metallic' properties: tensile strength, malleability, durability," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_a_n_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability
2. "MIMS 2 Applications discussions," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions
3. EPEMC & Diffusion Research, EPEMC Gateway- "Standards," 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/home/standards?authuser=0>
4. "Extended Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmology (EPEMCtm) Products & Papers Directory," EPEMC & Diffusion Research, EPEMC Gateway- EPEMC, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc>
5. "MIMS 1.12 - Self-Consistency of the "Big G" Diagram," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram
6. "FAQ: EPEMC & MIMS - Also, PEMS, HEGEME, and other obscure acronyms related to EPEMC research," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50912946/FAQ_EPEMC_MIMS
7. "Mankind in Amnesia," I. Velikovsky, 1982
8. "Ferris Wheels and the Dionysian Irony The subconscious drive of thrill, abandonment of caution, and the motifs of Amusement Park rides," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/37403915/Ferris_Wheels_and_the_Dionysian_Irony_The_subconscious_drive_of_thrill_abandonment_of_caution_and_the_motifs_of_Amusement_Park_rides
9. "MIMS 2.7-8 : War & Government; The Rise and Fall of US Military Dominance, from an Art of War perspective, and MIMS Analysis, as well as a short discussion of the history of failures of government programs from antiquity through the Great Enlightenment," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of_US_Military_Dominance_from_an_Art_of_War_perspective_and_MIMS_Analysis_as_well_as_a_short_discussion_of_the_history_of_failures_of_government_programs_from_antiquity_through_the_Great_Enlightenment
10. "Chapter 13: Digital to Analog Conversion and Sound," Texas.edu., J. Valvano & R.Yerraballi, 2020, http://users.ece.utexas.edu/~valvano/Volume1/E-Book/C13_DACSound.htm
11. "Chinese Natural Philosophæ (Physics) inExtended-Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmology, Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC
12. "Explication of the Versatility of the "BigG" diagram in MIMS 1.0 1," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0